

The Resource Recovery Toolbox

**Co-designing and curating a platform for
promoting circularity in sanitation and waste
management**

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Key messages

- The Resource Recovery Toolbox is an open-access knowledge platform that makes decision-support resources for resource recovery from organic waste streams easier to find, evaluate, and use, addressing a gap no existing platform had filled.
- Its structure, content categories, and interface features were shaped by direct engagement with practitioners, researchers, and decision-makers through card sorting exercises, usability testing, and a landscape review of comparable online knowledge platforms, so as to reflect how the intended users think and work with tools.
- Hosted on the Sustainable Sanitation Alliance (SuSanA) website and featuring an AI-powered chatbot to support intuitive natural language exploration of its content, the Toolbox is designed to grow over time as new resources are added and as contributions from the broader community of practice expand its reach.
- The Toolbox is available at <https://rrtoolbox.susana.org/en>¹.

Introduction

Across the world, sanitation and waste systems are increasingly being understood not just as infrastructure for disposing of waste, but as potential sources of valuable resources – water, energy, nutrients, and organic matter. Yet the shift toward resource recovery in practice has been slow, in part because the knowledge needed to plan and implement these approaches remains hard to access. Relevant decision-support resources exist, such as software tools, assessment frameworks, business model guides, datasets, case studies, but they are scattered across a wide range of publications, websites, and institutions. For a practitioner starting a composting project or assessing the feasibility of establishing a biogas facility, knowing where to look is itself a major challenge.

The Resource Recovery Toolbox was developed by the Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI) to address this challenge. Funded by Formas – the Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development, and developed in collaboration with Dotwerkstatt, Baobab Tech, and the Sustainable Sanitation Alliance (SuSanA), the platform collates and curates resources relevant to resource recovery from organic waste streams (such as wastewater, faecal sludge, organic municipal solid waste, manure, and other agricultural waste streams) and makes them searchable and accessible in one place.

Developing a platform that would be genuinely useful, rather than just comprehensive, required understanding how its intended users think, search, and work. This brief

¹ The URL <http://www.resource-recovery.info/> was used during earlier stages of the project, but it now re-directs to the current URL <https://rrtoolbox.susana.org/en>

describes the participatory process that shaped the Toolbox's design, the insights it generated, and how those insights were translated into the platform that was launched in 2025.

How the Toolbox was designed

After collecting an initial set of tools that could potentially be included in the Toolbox, we conducted three main activities to understand user needs and inform the platform's design. These were: a card sorting exercise to develop an intuitive content taxonomy, a landscape review of comparable online knowledge platforms, and usability testing with practitioners and researchers from across the globe. These activities ran alongside and informed the technical web development process.

Initial collation of content

Before the card sorting exercise could begin, the project team first needed to gather a working body of tools and resources to sort. The starting point was a set of 24 software-based decision-support tools previously reviewed by Ddiba et al. (2023), supplemented by other outputs from the UrbanCircle project (www.sei.org/urbancircle). Beyond these, the team conducted a broader search across academic literature, practitioner databases, and specialist platforms, tracing citations and scanning sector networks to identify additional relevant tools.

WHAT COUNTS AS A "TOOL"?

"Tool" in the context of the Resource Recovery Toolbox encompasses all decision-support resources such as software, datasets, frameworks, guidelines and manuals, case studies, training materials, and multimedia content, that can support the planning and implementation of resource recovery initiatives from organic waste streams.

The resulting collection of tools was large and varied, spanning many formats and topics. To manage this, the team held an internal workshop to define inclusion and exclusion criteria. Resources were included if they had practical applicability to real-world resource recovery contexts and if they focused on organic waste streams. Exclusions covered general reports without actionable content, resources focused on inorganic waste streams, project websites without standalone usable content, and resources that were no longer maintained. The workshop also produced working definitions for the main content-type categories, laying the groundwork for the taxonomy that the card sorting exercise would later refine and validate, as well as the glossary² that is on the Toolbox platform.

² See: <https://rrtoolbox.susana.org/en/glossary>

Card sorting: making sense of how users categorise content

One of the foundational design challenges for a platform holding hundreds of diverse resources is deciding how to organise them. Category structures that seem logical to the designers may not match how users think about their work. To address this, the project team conducted a card sorting exercise, a well-established method in information architecture and user experience design, adapted from the protocol developed by Harloff and Coxon (2007).

The team presented participants with cards representing a sample of resource recovery tools and resources and asked them to sort the cards into groups according to how they would naturally look for that kind of resource, and to name the groups they created. The team conducted the exercise with ten stakeholders drawn from the project's broad reference group, using both a physical card format and an online version via Canva³ to allow administration in different settings. Nine of the participants were present in Stockholm during the World Water Week in August 2024, which allowed for an in-person session, while the team conducted an online version of the exercise for the tenth participant.

The team then analysed the results to identify patterns in how participants grouped content and what labels they applied. Several categorisation dimensions emerged consistently: the type of content or resource (e.g. guidelines, software, case study); the type of waste being processed (e.g. faecal sludge, food waste); the resource being recovered (e.g. energy, nutrients); the stage of a project (e.g. planning, implementation, monitoring); the intended audience; and geography and language. Many participants also expressed a strong preference for being able to assign resources to more than one category simultaneously. These findings directly shaped the multi-dimensional taxonomy adopted in the Toolbox.

Benchmarking comparable platforms

Before designing the platform, the project team needed to understand what was already available, what existing platforms do well, where they fall short, and what gaps remain unaddressed. The team ran the benchmarking as a series of internal workshops, comparing and analysing a range of online knowledge platforms relevant to resource recovery, water and sanitation, and waste management.

The team conducted a structured review of platforms including the faecal sludge management (FSM) Toolbox, Sani-Hub, the Climate and Clean Air Coalition (CCAC) Resource Hub, the Global Methane Initiative Resource Hub, the SuSanA library, the International Solid Waste Association (ISWA) Knowledge Base, the Global Water Partnership (GWP) Toolbox (IWRM Action Hub), the Sanitation and Water for All (SWA) Tools Portal, and EGESTABASE, among others. For each platform, the team assessed a set of questions covering its purpose, target audience, ease of use, visual design, search and filtering functionality, content types, language accessibility, and contribution mechanisms. Table 1 summarises the categories of features assessed in

³ The online graphic design platform available at <https://www.canva.com/>

the benchmarking and the key observations that informed the Toolbox design (partly framed as opportunities for the Toolbox).

Table 1: Platform feature categories assessed in the benchmarking exercise, with key observations and design opportunities.

CATEGORY 1 Display and navigation	CATEGORY 2 Accessibility and openness	CATEGORY 3 Content and contribution
WHAT WE FOUND <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most platforms rated average on visual design and ease of navigation. • Search bars were often not prominently placed. • Filtering options were frequently buried or limited. 	WHAT WE FOUND <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many platforms require registration or restrict access. • Language coverage is limited on most platforms. • Few platforms offer multi-language filtering of content. 	WHAT WE FOUND <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content types are often homogeneous on most platforms. • Few mix guidelines, software, datasets, and multimedia. • User contribution mechanisms are rare.
OPPORTUNITY Invest in strong visual design, prominent search, and intuitive filtering from the homepage.	OPPORTUNITY Provide fully open access without registration, with a multilingual interface and filtering.	OPPORTUNITY Curate diverse resource types and enable community contributions.

Usability testing: understanding how practitioners search and navigate

Alongside the benchmarking, the team conducted usability testing sessions with twelve practitioners, researchers, and consultants working in resource recovery and related fields. Participants came from Africa, Asia, Latin America, and Europe, and included both those with extensive digital research habits and those whose primary resource-finding tool is an internet search engine. Each session paired one project team member as facilitator with one participant, lasted approximately 45–60 minutes, and followed a structured protocol informed by user experience and user interface research methods.

Sessions began with a short background conversation about the participant’s work and their typical resource-finding habits. Participants then attempted to complete a realistic task, such as finding resources relevant to setting up a composting facility, or assessing a biogas project, or developing a waste-derived fertiliser, using a selection of comparable platforms, while narrating their experience. The facilitator recorded observations across four categories: habits (how participants typically search and use resources), mental models (what they expect to find and how they expect to navigate), positive experiences (what worked well), and negative experiences (what confused or blocked them). The facilitator also noted any additional cross-cutting comments or observations that participants raised.

Several themes emerged consistently across participants and geographies; these findings, and the design responses they prompted, are set out in Table 2 in the section on usability insights.

What the co-design process produced

A multi-dimensional taxonomy for the Toolbox

A core output of the card sorting exercise was a taxonomy that reflects the categories practitioners actually use when thinking about their work, rather than categories that seem logical from a technical or academic standpoint. The Toolbox's taxonomy allows each resource to be tagged across multiple dimensions simultaneously, so a user can filter by waste stream, resource recovered, technology, project stage, content type, geography, and language, in any combination (see Figure 1).

Content types in the Toolbox include software, frameworks, guidelines and manuals, case studies, datasets, training materials, videos, games, and standards and certification documents. These emerged from the card sorting groupings rather than being defined in advance, and they have been validated against the vocabulary that users themselves applied when naming their groups.

Figure 1: The seven dimensions by which tools and resources in the Toolbox are categorised, enabling multi-dimensional filtering and content discovery.

Items can be tagged in one or more categories across the dimensions above. This multi-dimensional structure enables powerful filtering and discovery according to user needs and context.

The taxonomy categories were then used as the foundation for a standardised metadata template, developed to ensure that every tool in the Toolbox would be described in a consistent and comparable way. The template captures descriptive information about each tool, including its purpose, intended users, required skills, and case examples, as well as structured metadata tags drawn directly from the taxonomy dimensions, covering content type, waste streams addressed, resources recovered, technologies, themes, geography, and language. This structure means that the same

document used to draft a tool description also generates the tags that make it searchable and filterable on the platform, connecting the co-design process directly to how content is organised and discovered in the Toolbox.

A distinct niche in the landscape of online knowledge platforms

The benchmarking review confirmed a clear gap that the Toolbox was then designed to fill. While the broader landscape of online knowledge platforms for water, sanitation, and waste management is relatively well populated, no existing platform addresses decision-support tools for resource recovery from sanitation and organic waste streams with comparable breadth and specificity. Existing platforms tend to focus on narrower technology areas, serve particular institutional audiences, or prioritise content hosting over structured discoverability. On dimensions such as multi-dimensional filtering, open access without registration, and multilingual search functionality, as well as ease of use and visual design, the reviewed platforms varied considerably, with a number presenting limited functionality in one or more of these areas.

These findings suggested that a well-designed platform focused specifically on resource recovery decision-support tools could occupy a distinct and underserved position in the existing landscape, provided it prioritised usability, openness, and relevance to the diverse range of practitioners working in this field, from technical consultants and engineers in low- and middle-income urban contexts to policy advisors and academic researchers.

Design decisions grounded in usability insights

Table 2 summarises the key usability findings from testing and the design responses they prompted. Several patterns recurred across participant groups and geographies, suggesting they reflected genuine friction points rather than individual preferences. Beyond the individual fixes recorded in the table, testing revealed a broader principle: practitioners arrive at the Toolbox with a specific problem in mind, not a desire to browse. The platform's design needed to support goal-directed searching as the primary mode of interaction, with browsing and discovery as a secondary path for users who wanted to explore more broadly. This shaped decisions about the prominence of the search bar, the default display of results, and the structure of individual tool description pages.

Table 2: Key usability insights and the design responses they shaped in the Toolbox.

Usability insight	Design implication	Response in the Toolbox
Users begin on search engines and return to platforms they learn to trust	Platform credibility and search engine visibility matter as much as content quality	Hosted on the established SuSanA domain; SEO optimised; integrated with SuSanA community
Search bars that are hard to find cause rapid disengagement	Search functionality must be immediately visible and central on every page	Prominent search bar on homepage and throughout the

Usability insight	Design implication	Response in the Toolbox
Mandatory registration deters access, especially for first-time users	Full content access without creating an account	platform; advanced filters clearly accessible All resources openly accessible; no sign-up required to browse
Language and geography filters are essential for an internationally diverse audience	Filtering must cover country, region, and language as standard options	Multi-dimensional filtering including country, region, and interface language
Users prioritise recent resources and want publication year visible in results	Year of release or publication should appear in search result listings	Publication and release year displayed on all tool entries
Content type labels are expected and help users navigate quickly	Clear, consistent labelling of resource types from the search results level	Content type tags visible on all entries; filterable from the homepage
Case studies are valued but only when enough context is given to assess fit	Contextual metadata for case studies must include location, scale, and technology	Case studies tagged by country, region, technology, and waste stream
Downloading and sharing resources with colleagues is a routine workflow	Download and sharing functionality should require no extra steps	Direct download links and shareable URLs on all resource pages, where applicable

Building the platform

The insights from the three co-design activities were consolidated into a requirement specification and design brief that guided the selection of a web development partner. Through a procurement process, Dotwerkstatt, a Berlin-based web development company, was contracted to design and build the platform. Development proceeded iteratively, moving from wireframes through a prototype to the finished platform, with regular review and feedback sessions between the SEI team and Dotwerkstatt at each stage. The back-end is built in Joomla as the content management system, reflecting the requirement to integrate the Toolbox into the existing SuSanA website infrastructure while accommodating the multi-dimensional filtering and custom metadata fields the taxonomy required.

In parallel, SEI contracted Baobab Tech through its WASH AI initiative to develop and integrate an AI-powered chatbot interface. The chatbot allows users to explore the Toolbox through natural language queries in multiple languages, providing context-aware recommendations and making the platform accessible to users who are unfamiliar with technical terminology or whose working language is not English.

With the platform built and the metadata template in place, the team turned to populating the Toolbox with content. For each tool, information was gathered from multiple sources, including user manuals, associated publications, video tutorials, and developer websites, and structured according to the standardised template. Given the volume of tools and the repetitive nature of the structuring task, the team made systematic use of AI-assisted structuring of the tool descriptions, via a custom GPT⁴. Source materials for each tool were provided to the custom GPT, which then structured the tool description material according to the template. Team members then reviewed, verified, and refined each entry before upload. This approach made it feasible to populate the platform at scale within project timelines without compromising description quality or consistency.

The Toolbox is hosted on the SuSanA platform, embedding it within an established community of practice of water and sanitation professionals worldwide. Key features include structured, searchable entries with consistent metadata; advanced filtering across content type, waste stream, recovered resource, technology, theme, geography, and language; an AI-powered chatbot for natural language search; fully open access without registration; a tool submission function for community contributions; and integration with the SuSanA Discussion Forum.

Reaching the Toolbox's target audience

Dissemination of the Toolbox has been integrated into events and networks serving the sanitation, waste management, and circular economy communities. The platform was introduced to practitioners at the SuSanA Annual Meetings in 2023, 2024, and 2025, and at the IWA World Water Congress in Kigali in December 2023, as well as at the Innovations for the Blue Planet conference in Stockholm in April 2024. It was presented at a waste management practitioners' workshop in Nairobi in May 2024 and at the Swedish Nutrient Platform meeting in April 2025. A dedicated launch webinar was held in May 2025, followed by presentations at the Source Separation Summit in Helsingborg in June 2025 and the 7th IWA International Conference on eco-Technologies for Wastewater Treatment in Stockholm in June 2025. The platform was also featured in various sessions at the World Water Week in both 2024 and 2025.

Beyond events, the communications strategy has focused on embedding the Toolbox in the online spaces where the target audience already operates, including the SuSanA Forum, practitioner email networks, and LinkedIn, where newly added tool batches are announced on a rolling basis. The Toolbox has been featured and linked to by a range of partner organisations, including the RecoLab network, the Rich Earth Institute, the Eawag Circular Sanitation Toolbox page, Water Links, PEP Raja Ampat, the Global Wastewater Initiative, the Global Sanitation Graduate School, and the African Circular Economy Network.

⁴ For more about custom GPTs, see here <https://help.openai.com/en/articles/8554407-gpts-in-chatgpt>

Content partnerships have been central to building the catalogue. Several research institutes, intergovernmental initiatives, and practitioner networks have contributed tools from their own portfolios, spanning areas such as sanitation and resource recovery research, short-lived climate pollutant mitigation in the waste sector, and extended producer responsibility. These partnerships both expand the content base and signal the Toolbox's standing within relevant practitioner communities.

EARLY REACH AND ENGAGEMENT

BASED ON MATOMO ANALYTICS OVER THE FIRST 12 MONTHS

Although still in an early growth phase, the Toolbox has already reached users in seventy-nine countries who engage substantially with the platform, averaging over four minutes per visit, with nearly half returning and following links to external tools and resources more than two hundred times. It now hosts over one hundred and thirty tools and resources.

Looking ahead

The Toolbox is an operational platform in active growth, with content expanding through both internal curation and partner contributions. Immediate priorities include increasing coverage of under-represented technology areas and geographies, improving metadata completeness across existing entries, and strengthening the contributor pipeline so that tool developers can submit entries directly for review. User feedback on what is useful, what is missing, and what could work better is welcomed and will inform ongoing improvements to both content and interface.

The AI-powered search interface presents further opportunities for development. As the catalogue grows, the ability to surface relevant results from natural language queries becomes more valuable, and there is potential to enrich the chatbot's responses with contextual guidance rather than simple retrieval. How the Toolbox can contribute to the broader ecosystem of WASH-sector knowledge platforms, including through data sharing and interoperability, remains an open area of work.

The participatory process described in this brief rests on the premise that a knowledge platform is only as useful as its alignment with the people who use it. The card sorting, usability testing, and benchmarking exercises produced insights that materially changed decisions about content organisation, platform features, and positioning. Sustaining that alignment, as both the platform and the field continue to evolve, will require the same commitment to iteration that shaped the original design.

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